

1 Agent-based Model for the simulation of genetic
2 and environmental features in Colorectal Cancer
3 development

4 Marco Ledda^{1*}, Alessandro Pluchino^{1†} and Marco Ragusa^{2†}

5 ^{1*}Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Catania, Piazza
6 Università, 2, Catania, 95131, Italy.

7 ^{2*}Department of Biomedical and Biotechnological Sciences—Section of
8 Biology and Genetics, University of Catania, Piazza Università, 2,
9 Catania, 95131, Italy.

10 *Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): marco.ledda@dfa.unict.it;
11 Contributing authors: alessandro.pluchino@unict.it; mragusa@unict.it;

12 †These authors contributed equally to this work.

13 **Abstract**

14 *Complexity in cancer research has led to the creation of powerful analytical tools*
15 *for helping experimental in vivo and in vitro methods. These tools range from*
16 *systems of differential equations resolved in computer simulations, to lattice mod-*
17 *els and agent-based models (ABMs). These analytical methods are focused on*
18 *studying cell behavior and dynamic cell populations. Among these, those that*
19 *are increasingly used are ABMs because they can incorporate multi-scale fea-*
20 *tures ranging from the individual up to the population level, mixing rules based*
21 *on mathematical and conceptual parameters, and combining statistical/popula-*
22 *tion assumptions with individual heterogeneity. In this work, we present an ABM*
23 *that simulates tumor progression in a colonic crypt, with the aim of providing*
24 *an experimental in silico environment for testing results achieved in traditional*
25 *lab research, and developing alternative scenarios of tumor development. As the*
26 *first part of an ongoing project, the long-term goal is to reproduce and study, the*
27 *general evolutionary mechanisms of a biological system.*

28 **Keywords:** Agent-based Models, Colorectal cancer (CRC), Biological evolution,
29 Causal relations

1 Introduction

The construction of a generalized model that simulates tumor development in any tissue of our organism is a challenging task, encompassing various analytical and computational aspects. These difficulties arise from issues related to data availability, modelization, and data organization, as well as the complexity and irregularity of genomic and histological characteristics observed in different tumors [Plutynski \(2021\)](#). Consequently, researchers have tended to analyze various tumors as quasi-isolated phenomena, considering their specific cellular functions, phenotypes, and genotypes [Weinberg \(2013\)](#).

Among all cancer types, colorectal cancer (CRC) stands out as the only one for which a clear progression model exists. This model describes the progression from normal-neoplastic epithelium to metastasis in terms of the activation and suppression of a series of oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes, respectively [Fearon and Vogelstein \(1990\)](#). The theoretical model of CRC progression was developed based on statistical data on genetic mutation frequencies and chromosome deletions. Subsequent discoveries identified three genetic agents present in every human tumor: oncogenes, tumor suppressors, and stability genes [Vogelstein and Kinzler \(2004\)](#).

CRC progression is also characterized by other important genomic features, such as *chromosomal instability* (CIN), *microsatellite instability* (MSI), *DNA mismatch repair deficiency* (MMR), and DNA methylation, which is a well-studied epigenetic cause of tumor development [Grady and Carethers \(2008\)](#). The oncogenic multi-step process begins with the deregulation of the β -catenin pathway due to (**APC**) mutation, followed by additional somatic mutations that enhance cell proliferation (**Kras**) and apoptosis resistance (**TP53**) [Vogelstein and Kinzler \(2004\)](#). These genomic deregulations occur with varying frequencies in the ideal timeline of CRC development [Nguyen and Duong \(2018\)](#).

Efforts to describe, classify, and predict the origins and evolution of CRC have led to the development of various experimental tools, including *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico* models [Bürtin, Mullins, and Linnebacher \(2020\)](#); [Chen et al. \(2020\)](#); [Haupt et al. \(2021\)](#); [Johnston, Edwards, Bodmer, Maini, and Chapman \(2007\)](#); [Meineke, Potten, and Loeffler \(2001\)](#); [Michor, Iwasa, Lengauer, and Nowak \(2005\)](#); [Van Leeuwen et al. \(2009\)](#); [Williams, Hague, Manning, Van der Stappen, and Paraskeva \(1993\)](#). Each approach has its own strengths and limitations. *In vivo* animal models provide strong therapeutic evidence but may not always accurately represent human responses due to genetic differences [Banerjee and Quirke \(1998\)](#). *In vitro* models allow direct observation and control at the cellular level, but standardization of cellular features is required for reliable results, and colonic flora is absent [Banerjee and Quirke \(1998\)](#); [Williams et al. \(1993\)](#). *In silico* models, including agent-based models (ABM), offer a different approach by simulating individual agent behavior and interactions, allowing the emergence of dynamics coherent with real data [An, Mi, Dutta-Moscato, and Vodovotz \(2009\)](#); [Conti, Di Mauro, Pluchino, and Mulder \(2020\)](#); [Fichera, Pluchino, and Volpe \(2018\)](#); [Le Pira, Inturri, Ignaccolo, Pluchino, and Rapisarda \(2017\)](#); [Pluchino, Rapisarda, and Garofalo \(2011\)](#).

Advancements in computational power have facilitated the development of various computational methods, such as lattice models, off-lattice models, and cell-based

1 models, which can simulate key characteristics of cancer, including hypoxia, angiogen-
2 esis, drug delivery, cancer stem cells, immune system interactions, invasion of adjacent
3 tissues, and metastasis Metzcar, Wang, Heiland, and Macklin (2019).

4 For example, the phenomenon of *anoikis*¹, a well-studied process, can be effec-
5 tively simulated using lattice models, where cells have their own defined space. When
6 inter-cellular adhesion is weakened by mutations, and the pressure between cells
7 exceeds a specific threshold, representing the distance from the basement membrane,
8 detached cells undergo cell death T. Ingham-Dempster, Walker, and Corfe (2017).
9 Mono-crypt models have been extended to incorporate proliferation in multiple crypts
10 T.A. Ingham-Dempster, Rosser, Corfe, and Walker (2020). Other approaches involve
11 comparing cell-based spatial models, incorporating cell-cell adhesion and proliferation
12 changes in response to Wnt-signals, with stochastic one-dimensional models predicting
13 the evolution of monoclonal conversion Mirams, Fletcher, Maini, and Byrne (2012).
14 Genetic-focused models study the dynamics of cell populations within the crypt, con-
15 sidering them as evolving populations after changes in genotype frequencies. These
16 models compare genomic analysis with real data and agent-based models where sub-
17 clones are generated after acquiring driver mutations Niida, Mimori, Shibata, and
18 Miyano (2021).

19 Building upon these existing models and the theoretical work of Fearon-Vogelstein,
20 the purpose of this work is to develop an agent-based model that simulates cell
21 dynamics in the colonic crypt, also as an experimental environment for testing various
22 scenarios related to CRC development. Furthermore, our approach aims to integrate
23 genetic triggers, spatial and population constraints, as well as interactions with other
24 species (such as immune system-like cells). The model is designed to represent a
25 biological evolutionary system, considering cells in the crypt microenvironment as
26 individuals belonging to different populations and species, subject to evolutionary
27 mechanisms. This perspective is based on the understanding that biological systems
28 can be viewed as hierarchically nested networks, where each level represents a net-
29 work, and cells, as independent agents, are nodes composed by networks of organs and
30 proteins working together to carry out cellular functions, and at the higher level, they
31 build networks who represent the cellular species Tëmkin and Eldredge (2015).

32 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief
33 description of the phenomenon from a biological perspective and outlines the features
34 of the model. In Section 3, we describe and explain the results obtained from the simu-
35 lations. Section 4 discusses the implications of the results, while Section 5 summarizes
36 the work and presents future directions.

37 2 Methods

38 2.1 Biological background

39 Colonic crypts represent invaginations within the colon tissue, serving as dynamic
40 structures where enterocytes, which are the intestinal epithelial cells, undergo a series
41 of coordinated movements. These enterocytes are generated by stem cells located at

¹*Anoikis* is a particular form of programmed cell death, triggered when a tissue cell detaches from the extracellular matrix.

1 the base of the crypt and ascend towards the crypt mouth, ultimately reaching the
2 lumen of the colon. During this continuous movement, enterocytes receive signaling
3 molecules known as Wnt signals from neighboring mesenchymal cells. These signals
4 play a crucial role in stimulating the production of β -catenin, a protein that exhibits a
5 descending gradient along the crypt, with higher concentrations at the base [Humphries](#)
6 [and Wright \(2008\)](#); [Weinberg \(2013\)](#). Enterocytes possessing elevated levels of β -
7 catenin are referred to as *Transit-amplifying* cells. These cells display characteristics
8 similar to stem cells and exhibit vigorous proliferation, thereby ensuring a constant
9 supply of new cells in the crypt. As enterocytes migrate upward, the concentration of
10 β -catenin gradually decreases. This reduction allows the cells to undergo differentia-
11 tion, assuming specific functions, and eventually undergo apoptosis within a span of 3
12 to 5 days [Van Der Flier and Clevers \(2009\)](#); [Weinberg \(2013\)](#). This process represents
13 an extraordinary mechanism for safeguarding against cellular dysfunctions resulting
14 from DNA damage or other challenges arising within the intestinal microenvironment
15 [Weinberg \(2013\)](#).

16 2.2 The model

17 The model is an off-lattice model designed with the ABMs software Netlogo [Wilen-](#)
18 [sky \(1999\)](#). The interface shows the world, a 2D representation of the colonic crypt
19 arranged as if the crypt is an unfolded cylinder.

Fig. 1 Cell typologies: blue cells *Transit-amplifying*, and green cells *Differentiated*.

20 2.3 World Structure

21 The chosen population size corresponds to the median crypt, typically consisting of
22 2000-2500 cells arranged in a diameter of 25 cells per line. In the model, the epithelium

Table 1 Cell variables

Main Cell Variables	Values
Lifetime	Normal = min 96 h (hours), max 120 h, Tumoral = min 96 h, max 150 h
Mitosis time	Normal distribution ¹ mean = Mitosis mean time, variance 1
Mitosis mean time	Normal (transit-amplifying) = 24 or 16 h with K-ras mutations = 12
Beta-cat	Descendent gradient set at 1 in the bottom 0 in the top of the crypt
Pre-adenoma	Boolean variable true if both APC = [1 1]
Adenoma	Boolean variable true if APC = [1 1] and K-ras = [1 0] or [0 1]
Tumoral	Boolean variable true if APC = [1 1], K-ras = [1 0] and P53 = [1 1]

1 undergoes renewal every 3-5 days, indicating that each cell has a timeframe of 72 to
2 120 hours to either reach the crypt mouth or undergo cell death [Yatabe, Tavaré, and](#)
3 [Shibata \(2001\)](#). The height of the crypt in the model is represented by the number of
4 cell layers, which is set at 100 cells. Each time step in the simulation, corresponding
5 to 1 hour (1 tick of the program), the cells move forward. With each cell occupying
6 a length of 3 patches and a width of 1, the world size is set at 300 x 50 patches. By
7 assigning an age equals to 0 for cells in the first line and equals to 100 for cells in
8 the last line that do not die during migration, the maximum migration time closely
9 aligns with reality [Baker et al. \(2014\)](#); [Nowak \(2006\)](#). In the crypt-world, cells of the
10 two types are distributed in a predefined proportion, with approximately 75% being
11 *Differentiated* cells and 25% being *Transit-amplifying* cells [T. Ingham-Dempster et al.](#)
12 [\(2017\)](#).

13 Considering the crypt as an unfolded cylinder, the model adopts horizontal periodic
14 boundary conditions for the world. When cells reach the topmost cell line, they exit
15 the simulation and are no longer considered in the model dynamics.

16 2.4 Agents

17 Agents represent cells divided into two physiological typologies: *transit-amplifying* cells
18 and *differentiated* cells; and into three neoplastic typologies: *pre-adenoma*, *adenoma*,
19 and *tumoral* cells. See the list of the relevant dynamic variables in Table 1.

20 Each individual cell, depicted in Fig. 2, carries out its activities autonomously
21 while occupying a specific position (patch) within the world. The movement and mitosis
22 of cells are influenced by their interactions with neighboring cells. This modeling

¹We assumed that the distribution of mitotic time is well represented by a normal distribution, which is typical, for some features, in biological populations.

1 approach is chosen to preserve the individual heterogeneity of cell behavior while capturing population-level characteristics. In the physiological state, cells have a single degree of freedom for movement. They are allowed to advance one patch forward only if the patch ahead of them is unoccupied, as illustrated in the first image in Fig. 3. This movement mechanism ensures a continuous flow of cells from the bottom to the top of the crypt.

7 As cells are not created with the same age, some of them die during migration, leaving empty spaces within the cell line. To address this issue, all cell types are capable of entering mitosis to fill these gaps. When an empty space occurs, a neighboring cell randomly undergoes mitotic activity to occupy the vacant position.

11 Another challenge arises when a cell reaches its mitosis time but nearby spots are not empty. In such cases, the mitotic cell eliminates a neighboring cell with a lower number of mitotic activities or a higher lifetime. These processes align with biological plausibility, as a cell can be eliminated based on the number of times it has proliferated (linked to fitness) or its age. This allows for more efficient or younger cells to take their place, as observed in biological systems [Di Gregorio, Bowling, and Rodriguez \(2016\)](#).

Fig. 2 Cell behavior algorithm.

17 2.5 Genetic features and mutation effects

18 Every cell has a set of genes, see Table 2, chosen following the CRC progression already described (see 1).

20 In our model, each of the three genes controls a simplified action to avoid excessive complexity. We adopt the one-hit hypothesis for oncogenes (*Kras* in this model) and

Table 2 Gene characteristics

Genes	State
APC	wild type = [0 0], heterozygote = [1 0] [0 1], mutated = [1 1] (positive effect in the model)
K-ras	wild type = [0 0], heterozygote = [1 0] [0 1], (positive effect in the model)
P53	wild type = [0 0], heterozygote = [1 0] [0 1], mutated = [1 1] (positive effect in the model)
Regulation genes (N = 50)	N = [[0 0], [0 1], ..., [1 0]] determine different phenotypes of tumoral cells, apoptosis, resistance to the immune system

1 the two-hit hypothesis for tumor suppressor genes (*APC* and *P53*). According to these
2 hypotheses, a single allele mutation is sufficient to enhance the function of oncogenes,
3 while both alleles of a tumor suppressor gene must be mutated for its function to be
4 affected [Vogelstein and Kinzler \(2004\)](#).

5 To incorporate the characteristic of Loss of Heterozygosity (LOH) [Nowak et al.](#)
6 [\(2002\)](#), we set the probability of point mutation in the second allele to be one order
7 of magnitude lower than the probability of mutation in the first allele [Michor, Iwasa,](#)
8 [and Nowak \(2004\)](#). Specifically, if the probability of mutation in the first allele is x_1 ,
9 then the probability of mutation in the second allele is $x_2 > x_1$. The tumor sup-
10 pressor gene *APC*, even when heterozygous, has a positive function in controlling the
11 differentiation of cells from *transit-amplifying* to *differentiated* state. However, muta-
12 tion of both alleles in *APC* disrupts the regulation of β -catenin, preventing cells from
13 differentiating. This can lead to the migration of transit-amplifying cells to regions
14 of the crypt where only differentiated, non-proliferative, and functional cells should
15 be present. Additionally, we introduce a slight deviation in the forward movement of
16 cells to simulate a slower rate of migration, which may contribute to cell accumula-
17 tion after mitosis. Regarding the *Kras* gene, mutation of one allele increases the mean
18 proliferation time [Liu, Jakubowski, and Hunt \(2011\)](#). Refer to [Table 1](#) for detailed
19 information.

20 The wild type version of *TP53*, known as the *genome Gatekeeper* [Weinberg \(2013\)](#),
21 plays a crucial role in cell regulation. In its wild type homozygote form, it ensures that
22 cells with significant DNA errors, defined as having more than half of the 50 regulation
23 genes mutated, undergo apoptosis. However, when both alleles of *TP53* are mutated,
24 it increases the probability of mutation in all other genes. Specifically, the probability
25 exponent decreases by 0.5 unit for each mitosis until cellular death. The precise quan-
26 titative analysis for this phenomenon is not available in the literature, so we chose
27 a decrease that is neither too pronounced nor insufficient, aiming to simulate DNA
28 deregulations realistically. It is worth noting that *TP53* is described in the literature
29 as a tumor suppressor gene involved in crucial aspects of neoplastic and metastatic
30 processes, such as proliferation, resistance to apoptosis, and migration [Rivlin, Brosh,](#)

1 [Oren, and Rotter \(2011\)](#); [Weinberg \(2013\)](#)). Therefore, it seemed appropriate to simu-
2 late the various functions of *TP53* by augmenting the overall probability of mutation
3 in other genes.

4 Although there is no specific temporal order for the occurrence of mutated genes
5 in neoplastic typologies, except for *APC* which alone accounts for the *pre-adenoma*
6 typology, various combinations of mutated genes lead to different types of neoplasms.
7 When a cell acquires the *pre-adenoma* typology, instead of moving in a straight line,
8 it inclines randomly to the right or left, as depicted in the second image from the left
9 in Fig. 3. If, in addition to *APC* mutation, the *Kras* gene also undergoes mutation,
10 the cell transitions to the *adenoma* typology. Cells with the *adenoma* typology exhibit
11 the same movement pattern as *pre-adenoma* cells but proliferate at a faster rate, as
12 shown in the third figure, 3.

13 The final phenotypic change occurs with the addition of *TP53* mutation, resulting
14 in the *tumoral* typology. In this state, cells are unable to move around but can pro-
15 liferate in all positions rather than just adjacent spaces, as illustrated in the fourth
16 figure, 3.

Fig. 3 Cell movement based on cell type: *Transit-amplifying* cells are represented by blue cells, *differentiated* cells by green cells, *adenoma* cells by orange cells, and *tumoral* cells by violet cells. Arrows indicate the degree of angular freedom during movement and mitosis. In the last panel, the arrows are dashed red lines because *tumoral* cells can only enter mitosis in the permitted direction, but they can no longer move.

17

18 2.6 Micro-environmental features

19 Genetic factors are well-established triggers of cancer transformation in many types of
20 cancer. However, representing the influence of environmental factors poses a greater
21 challenge.

22 Our current understanding of the tumor micro-environment (TME) highlights the
23 complexity of elements present in our body from the early stages of tumor develop-
24 ment to metastasis [Anderson and Simon \(2020\)](#). These elements play a role in either
25 promoting or inhibiting tumor progression. Simulating every specific molecular inter-
26 action within the TME would be impractical and inconsistent with the intended scope
27 of the model. Therefore, we have chosen to represent immune system cells as a combi-
28 nation of natural killer cells (NK) and macrophages (M1 and M2) to account for the
29 complexity of the TME.

30 Another important environmental feature in our model is the population as an
31 entity. Over-proliferating cells tend to create hypoxic niches, where cells situated at

1 a certain distance from the nearest blood vessel are subjected to a lack of oxygen
2 [Al Tameemi, Dale, Al-Jumaily, and Forsyth \(2019\)](#). To capture this phenomenon, we
3 incorporate the concept of hypoxia and its effects on cell survival.

4 The interaction between epithelial cells and environmental features follows spe-
5 cific rules. A cell count is performed in each spot, and when a threshold is reached,
6 immune system cells appear and move randomly within the TME. If these immune cells
7 encounter a non-physiological cell, they move toward it and eliminate it, mimicking
8 spatial interactions. The same cell count procedure also activates another threshold,
9 which represents the maximum number of non-hypoxic cells allowed in a given spot.

10 By incorporating these rules, we aim to capture the essential aspects of the inter-
11 action between epithelial cells and the TME, while simplifying the representation of
12 complex molecular interactions and spatial dynamics.

13 3 Results

14 In our model, the starting values of cellular genotypes can be set to homozygous wild-
15 type, homozygous mutated, or heterozygotes (e.g., [0 0] and [1 1] or [0 1], [1 1]). The
16 initial probability distribution for these genotypes can be adjusted using a slider in
17 the model interface, ranging from 0 to 1. A value of 0 indicates that all cells start with
18 a homozygous wild-type genotype, while a value of 1 means that all cells start with a
19 heterozygous genotype. This feature is designed to account for the stem-niche hypoth-
20 esis, which suggests that mutations can also occur within stem cells, allowing stem
21 cell clones to invade the entire crypt [Humphries and Wright \(2008\)](#). Although stem
22 cells are not explicitly included in the model dynamics, this characteristic preserves
23 the possibility of stem cell involvement.

24 To observe changes in the dynamics of cell population growth, the rate of cell
25 death due to physiological and environmental causes (e.g., immune system-mediated
26 killing or overcrowding), and the rate of cell death due to aging of tumoral cells, we
27 conducted several runs with three different stop conditions: *a*) one year has passed; *b*)
28 the proportion of *transit-amplifying* and *differentiated* cells is inverted; *c*) the crypt
29 population reaches 10,000 individuals.

30 To analyze the effects of varying mutation probabilities, we adjusted the probability
31 of gene mutation from 10^{-9} to 10^{-2} while keeping the other parameters constant.
32 This range covers a wide spectrum of mutation probabilities and allows for meaningful
33 comparisons with other models that have used similar values [Michor et al. \(2005,](#)
34 [2004\)](#). By examining seven scenarios with different mutation probabilities, we can gain
35 insights into how changes in mutation rates impact cell behavior and overall system
36 dynamics. The other fixed parameters were:

- 37 • **number of immune system's cells:** 1 / hour
- 38 • **number of cells that a killer cells eliminates before die:** 5 cells
- 39 • **hypoxic threshold:** 5 cells / patch
- 40 • **probability of starting genotype:** $P = 0.5$

41 The chosen parameter values in our model are based on qualitative and quantitative
42 descriptions from the literature [Al Tameemi et al. \(2019\)](#); [Guo et al. \(2019\)](#). While

1 some parameters, such as the concentration of immune system cells produced per hour
2 and the number of *tumoral* cells that an immune system cell can kill before dying, are
3 not known at the level of individual cells, we have incorporated them in the model as
4 approximate representations of their effects. Similarly, the hypoxic threshold is stated
5 at $150 \mu\text{m}$, but the exact number of epithelial cells from a hypothetical blood vessel
6 is not necessary in the context of our model.

7 The population dynamics variations are depicted in Figure 4. Plot A) illustrates the
8 constant populations of *transit-amplifying* and *differentiated* cells observed throughout
9 the simulation period of one model-year across multiple experiments with mutation
10 probabilities ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} . This panel provides a representative overview,
11 demonstrating the consistent behavior of these cell types.

12 In plot B), with a mutation probability of 10^{-6} , minor expansions of the transit-
13 amplifying population occur, attributed to the emergence of *adenomatous* and *pre-*
14 *adenoma* mutations. Moreover, these expansions cause a restriction of *differentiated*
15 population.

16 Plot C) shows that cellular population is subjected to fluctuations, alternat-
17 ing between growth and regression of *adenoma* and *pre-adenoma* phenotypes, thus
18 resulting in some sort of homeostatic behavior, fighting neoplastic variants.

19 Both plots D), E) and F) exhibit similar trends, with a significant increase in
20 both the *tumoral* and *adenoma* populations. The tendency of the system to bounce
21 back towards a stable physiological equilibrium, is challenged by the high probabili-
22 ty of mutation, responsible of the uncontrolled proliferation of *tumoral* phenotypes,
23 especially, in scenarios E) and F).

24 Furthermore, a periodic trend in the immune system cell population emerges,
25 closely matching the *pre-adenoma* and *adenoma* phenotypes in terms of timing. This
26 periodicity exhibits characteristics resembling a predator-prey relationship.

27 In all the simulations conducted with mutation probabilities ranging from 10^{-9} to
28 10^{-7} , there were no significant differences in the death rates per hour, as depicted in
29 Figure (5, A). The death rate remained relatively constant at approximately 140 cells
30 per hour. In the scenario with a mutation probability of 10^{-6} , significant changes in
31 the death rates were noted. There was an increase in the rate of normal deaths, up to
32 160, along with a rise in other modes of death, such as death resulting from local over-
33 grouping (referred to as *Hypoxic death*) and cells being killed by the immune system
34 (*Immune sys death*). An interesting observation is the absence of a significant death
35 rate among aged tumoral cells, possibly due to the fact that very few, if any, can evade
36 the environmental factors causing their demise (see Figure 5, B).

37 The results of genotype frequencies revealed a satisfying visual correspondence
38 between the flow of genes within populations and the dynamics of the population, see
39 Fig. 6.

40 In Panel A), the genetic flow remains constant, reflecting the stable population
41 dynamics at a mutation probability of 10^{-9} . All phenotypes maintain the initial geno-
42 type inherited from stem cells, after the first 120 hours of total renewal of the crypt
43 epithelium.

44 In Panel B), the frequency changes are shown corresponding to the clonal expan-
45 sions observed in the population plot. There are several expansions attributed to

Fig. 4 Population dynamics in function of the hours: abbreviations are referred to cells typologies: *Transit-amplifying*, *Differentiated*, *Pre-adenoma*, *Adenoma*, *Tumoral*, *Immune-system cells*. A) shows the size of the cell populations in crypts with gene probability of mutation in the scenarios ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} . B) populations size with probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-6} . C) populations size with probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-5} . D) populations size with probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-4} . E) populations size with probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-3} . F) populations size with probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-2} .

1 *adenoma* mutations with an interesting increase in wild type version of *KRAS*, after
 2 the first *adenoma* expansion.

3 Panel C) illustrates the gene flow within the crypt when the mutation probability
 4 is set to 10^{-2} . In this scenario, the most prevalent genotypes are those with $APC =$
 5 $[0-0]$, $Kras = [1-1]$, and $P53 = [1-1]$.

6 Interesting results emerged concerning the number of proliferation events for each
 7 phenotype, see Fig. 7. In fact, normal cells seem to have a skewed normal distribution,
 8 panel A), while *adenoma* and *tumoral* cells showed a very wide normal distribution
 9 with a nearly shared mean value, panel B) and C). A relevant aspect of these distri-
 10 butions is that whilst the mean mitotic-time is assigned for every phenotype, when
 11 the probability of mutation is increased up to 10^{-2} the normal distributions of mitosis
 12 are progressively transformed. If we observe panel B) both *pre-adenoma* and *adenoma*
 13 phenotypes have a clear distribution with an evident average interval; instead, in
 14 panel C) *pre-adenoma* phenotype seems to have almost a bimodal distribution. These

Fig. 5 Here, various types of cell deaths occurring per hour are presented. *Normal death* indicates the number of cells that have died due to physiological causes, such as reaching their maximum life threshold or being killed by another physiological cell to facilitate mitotic activity. *Hypoxic death* refers to cells that have died after the hypoxic threshold is reached. *Immune sys death* represents the number of cells killed by the immune system. *Tumoral death* accounts for tumoral cells that have died due to reaching the age threshold, which is set at 150 hours. A) illustrates different scenarios, ranging from crypts with a probability of mutation as low as 10^{-9} up to 10^{-7} . B) specifically focuses on the scenario with a probability of mutation set at 10^{-6} .

1 features are probably due to the sparse space arrangement of *pre-adenoma* and *ade-*
 2 *noma* phenotypes, whose movement create random mitotic spots where environmental
 3 conditions differ, see Fig. 10.

4 Another notable feature was the cell density, which increased up to 7 cells per spot
 5 for a mutation probability exceeding 10^{-7} , as illustrated in Figure (8). The power-law
 6 distribution observed in the arrangement of cells on the crypt surface is consistent
 7 with patterns seen in other biological systems. This distribution, characterized by a
 8 few elements possessing a particular attribute while the majority is in the long tail of
 9 the distribution [Koonin, Wolf, Karev, Almaas, and Barabási \(2006\)](#). In this context,
 10 specific patches act as hubs for the majority of cells.

11 3.1 Discussion

12 The purpose of developing this model was to create a tool for theoretical investigations,
 13 hypothesis generation, and experimental design related to a biological phenomenon.
 14 Modeling complex biological phenomena is inherently challenging, and therefore, we
 15 would like to reflect on the variable choices, parameter ranges, and the consistency of
 16 our results with other studies.

17 The variables within the model are intentionally designed to allow extensive manip-
 18 ulation of parameters, even in scenarios that may not have immediate biological
 19 relevance or experimental basis. This flexibility is exemplified, for example, by the
 20 ability to set the physiological cell lifespan to just 1 hour, or allow physiological cells

Fig. 6 The abbreviations used refer to the names of genes. For example, apc 00 represents the gene *APC* with both alleles being wild type, apc 10 - 01 represents heterozygosity, and apc 11 represents both alleles being mutated. The same conventions apply to the other two genes, *Kras* and *P53*. A) This scenario illustrates the frequencies of the genes in the cell population when the probability of mutation ranges from 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} . B) This scenario displays the frequencies of the genes in cells with a probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-6} . C) This scenario displays the frequencies of the genes in cells with a probability of mutation chosen at 10^{-2} .

1 to enter in mitotic activity regardless of their neighborhood, which are not reason-
 2 able choices, biologically speaking. However, this choices could be motivated by the
 3 fact that this model serves as more than just an environment for replicating colorectal
 4 cancer (CRC) development. It provides a platform for theoretical inquiries into causal
 5 relationships within a biologically inspired system.

6 Detecting causal relationships in traditional *in vivo* and *in vitro* research can be
 7 challenging due to the complex nature of entities and interactions involved, as well
 8 as the difficulty of conducting counterfactual scenarios. However, within a precisely
 9 controlled environment offered by this model, an interventionist account of causal-
 10 ity Woodward (2010); Woodward and Woodward (2005) can be applied with greater
 11 power. The manipulability of the model allows for the exploration of intrinsic and
 12 extrinsic interactions that contribute to the neoplastic phenomenon Rondeau, Lar-
 13 monier, Pradeu, and Bikfalvi (2019), although further analysis is required at other
 14 levels. For example, the current model represents driver genes as causal agents with
 15 precise effects, without considering any reciprocal influence. This means that the

Fig. 7 Proliferation distributions. Panel (A) shows the mitotic distribution in the physiological scenario. Panel (B) is taken from scenario at 10^{-6} with the emergence of both, *pre-adenoma* and *adenoma* cells. Panel (C) shows the scenario at 10^{-2} , where all the neoplastic typologies are present.

Fig. 8 Cells per patch. Here is portrayed a snapshot of the distribution of the cells per surface units (patches).

- 1 altered movement resulting from *APC* suppression does not directly affect the proliferation time, which only increases after *Kras* mutation. However, the large population
- 2 of cells in the same location influencing each other and potentially leading to cell death
- 3 can be considered as a top-down influence or a constraint that shapes subsequent cellular behavior within the spatial context [Bechtel \(2017\)](#); [Ellis \(2012\)](#); [Tëmkin and](#)
- 4 [Eldredge \(2015\)](#).
- 5
- 6

1 Regarding the initial genotype condition of the cell population, all the runs were
 2 conducted with a starting probability of heterozygosis set to 0.5. However, it is impor-
 3 tant to note that in each generation cycle, 50% of stem cells could potentially have a
 4 mutated allele. Therefore, it is necessary to perform tests with other starting values,
 5 such as a completely healthy population of stem cells with wild-type genes (i.e., prob-
 6 ability of heterozygosis set to 0). It is also worth mentioning that the model represents
 7 an idealized crypt without specific characteristics unique to any particular human or
 8 murine individual. Therefore, aspects such as the one-year simulation period or the
 9 number of cells required to trigger the population stop condition (10,000 cells) do not
 10 reflect the characteristics of patients at specific ages or tumor stages.

11 Further testing is needed for parameters related to immune system cells and over-
 12 grouping deaths. For example, a minimal genetic model of tumor development can be
 13 explored by setting the number of immune cells to 0 and the hypoxic threshold to a
 14 large number. In this scenario, we would expect to observe distinct tumor development
 15 once the first neoplastic cell arises. Consistent with the Vogelstein model, we observed
 16 that in all simulations where neoplastic phenotypes emerged, cells initially assumed
 17 the *pre-adenoma* phenotype (i.e., *APC* mutation) or at most the *adenoma* phenotype
 18 (possibly because *Kras* acts as an oncogene even with one mutated allele, and genotype
 19 frequencies indicate that the majority of the population is heterozygous for *Kras*).

20 A model constructed using data and assumptions from the literature should pro-
 21 vide results that are, at least, consistent with the current state of the art. From our
 22 perspective, this consistency is evident from two aspects. Firstly, the visual representa-
 23 tion of the cell arrangement in the crypt within the NetLogo environment aligns with
 24 the phenomenon known as *Intra-tumoral Heterogeneity* (ITH) [Zheng et al. \(2020\)](#), as
 25 depicted in Fig. (10, 1-6). Secondly, from a quantitative standpoint, the model's design,
 26 such as proliferation events measured by crypt height, is similar to those observed in
 27 other CRC studies [Zhao and Michor \(2013\)](#), as shown in Fig. (9), where the majority
 28 of mitotic events occur within the *transit-amplifying* population.

Fig. 9 Mitotic activity based on crypt height.

29 The visual aspect of the crypts reveals a significant difference between those with a
 30 probability of mutation set at 10^{-9} (panel 1) in Fig. 10) and those with a probability of
 31 mutation set at 10^{-6} or higher (panels 2-6). When comparing the population dynamics

1 within the range of 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} , we observe a phenomenon similar to a phase transition.
 2 Furthermore, within the range of 10^{-3} to 10^{-2} , we observe behavior associated
 3 with cells exhibiting chromosomal instability (CIN) Nowak et al. (2002). This behavior
 4 is characterized by a rapid growth of the total cellular population (4,000-6,000
 5 individuals) occurring within 100-150 hours.

Fig. 10 Crypt final states: starting from the left panel we have six snapshots of the nine final stages simulated scenarios. 1) This scenario represents the physiological state of a healthy crypt, with *Transit-amplifying* and *Differentiated* cells positioned correctly along the height of the crypt and in the appropriate proportions. This physiological state remains the same even when the probability of mutation is fixed at 10^{-8} and 10^{-7} . 2) In this scenario, changes occur, and we observe a cluster of adenomatous cells being attacked by immune-system cells. 3) This scenario represents a probability of mutation of 10^{-5} , with no qualitative changes in the emergence and types of mutated phenotypes. 4) In this scenario, the probability of mutation is 10^{-4} , and a distinction arises between two mutated phenotypes with different local displacements. 5) This scenario corresponds to a probability of mutation of 10^{-3} , where there is a much more pronounced Intratumor Heterogeneity (ITH), with the first mutated cells emerging at the level of *Differentiated* cells. 6) Here, the probability of mutation is 10^{-3} , and we observe a completely deregulated crypt with evident ITH. Additionally, *Transit-amplifying* cells migrate towards the crypt mouth, which is an abnormal occurrence in a healthy crypt.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we try to introduce a new type of model that takes into account both genetic and environmental components. **SMT** (*somatic mutation theory*) and **TOFT** (*tissue organization field theory*) are the two main paradigms used in cancer research that represent these two aspects. The first one assumes that multiple consecutive gene mutations in one cell, which proliferate more than the others, spread the tumoral phenotype and are the primary cause of tumor emergence and development. The second states that environmental factors account for these alterations in the signaling between cellular populations in adjacent tissues, which results in gene mutations Bertolaso (2016); Soto and Sonnenschein (2011).

The connection between these two aspects, even if it is oversimplified, is built in a way that is consistent with what cancer research indicates, namely that it is not just a matter of mutation and hyperproliferation. The presence or absence of immune system cells favors the rise of one cell typology over another, and an elevated number of cells in a small space causes cells to die. Additional research should provide more precise evidence of correlations (and hopefully causal relationships) between system variables and environmental factors that affect the dynamics of different cell typologies. Moreover, future work will aim to incorporate additional features at the genetic and cellular levels, such as energy consumption based on cell typology, a more detailed model of gene regulatory networks for driver genes, and a more sophisticated interaction between crypt cells and immune system cells.

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